

Vanadium. Part III. Vanadium (IV) and Vanadium (V) Complexes of Substituted Aromatic Hydroxamic Acids

R. L. Dutta and Subrata Lahiry

Co-ordination complexes of vanadium in 4⁺ and 5⁺ oxidation states have been studied with eleven substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids. Besides isolating the oxo-hydroxo-bis-hydroxamato-vanadium (V) (A) complexes with all the ligands, it has been further possible to describe some crystalline, highly coloured, ester-like compounds, namely, oxo-alkoxo-bis-hydroxamato-vanadium (V) (B). Quadrivalent vanadium complexes of a few ligands of the type oxo-bis-hydroxamato-vanadium (IV) (C) have also been prepared and their properties examined. Some of the complexes of types (A) and (C) have also been isolated in differently coloured modifications.

The colour reaction of these ligands with traces of vanadate in aqueous alcoholic medium has also been studied. These results confirm our earlier findings on benzohydroxamic acid, namely, the formation of a 1:3 metal: ligand complex.

The interesting results of vanadium-benzohydroxamic acid system¹ have led to the present investigation on a large number of variously substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids as ligands towards vanadium to throw more light on the co-ordination chemistry of vanadium. Our interest was particularly directed to the ester-like vanadium (V) complexes and the paramagnetic vanadium (IV) complexes. In Table I are included the substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids along with their complexes with vanadium.

TABLE I

Reagents.	Complexes.		
	B.	A.	C.
1. $C_6H_5CH_2.CONHOH$	$[VO(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$ (i) Violet (ii) Blue	$[VO(OX)(R'H)_2]$ X=Me and Et,
2. $C_6H_5CH=CH.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
3. $C_{10}H_7.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OX)(R'H)_2]$ X=Me, Et, Pr ⁿ , Pr ⁱ , Bu and C_3H_{11}
4. $C_6H_6N.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
5. $p-(NO_2).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	$[VO(R'H)_2]$ (i) Violet (ii) Green	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OX)(R'H)_2]$ X=Me and Et
6. $p-(CH_3).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	$[VO(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
7. $p-(OCH_3).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	$[VO(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
8. $p-(OH).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
9. $m-(NO_2).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	$[VO(R'H)_2]$	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
10. $o(OH).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..
11. $o(NH_2).C_6H_4.CONHOH$	..	$[VO(OH)(R'H)_2]$	..

$R'H_n =$ a molecule of substituted aromatic hydroxamic acid.

Phenylacetylhydroxamic acid is found to react with ammonium vanadate at pH 3-4, producing a deep violet compound of the composition $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$. This is diamagnetic and readily soluble in alcohols from which medium it has been possible to isolate some beautiful, glistening, dark ruby-red crystals of composition $[\text{VO}(\text{OX})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$ ($\text{X}=\text{Me}$ and Et). The analytical results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Compound.	Calculated.				Found.			
	%V.	%N.	%C.	%H.	%V.	%N.	%C.	%H.
$[\text{VO}(\text{OMe})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$	12.91	7.03	51.25	4.77	12.6	7.1	51.04	4.83
$[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}'\text{Me})_2]$	12.38	6.79	52.42	5.09				
$[\text{VO}(\text{OH} \dots \text{OHMe})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$	12.26	6.72	49.03	5.05				

The results undoubtedly point to presence of one alkyl group per entity of the complex $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$ and discard the possibility of the formation of an alcohol adduct as also of the total esterification of the ligand molecule. These also show diamagnetic behaviour. Further, these are non-electrolytes in methanol.

α -Naphthylhydroxamic acid also produces with vanadate a violet-black product which reacts with alcohols with extreme ease and a series of ester compounds has been obtained in the form of red to orange-red crystals. It has been possible to isolate ester compounds with methanol, ethanol, propanol¹³, isopropanol, butanol¹⁴, and amyl¹⁵ alcohol. Here also, the analyses strongly support the view that only one alkyl group is present in the molecule.*

Cinnamylhydroxamic acid and quinaldinohydroxamic acids have also furnished the violet-black precipitate. These dissolve in alcohols, forming a deep red solution from which, however, no red-coloured ester compounds could be isolated; instead, evaporation of the solution gives back only the original violet-black compound. This had the same analytical values as the original violet-black compound.

p-Nitrobenzohydroxamic acid gives a violet-coloured oxo-hydroxo-bis-*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamato-vanadium (V). This reacts with methanol and ethanol to produce the corresponding ester compounds. These are brick-red in colour and give diamagnetic susceptibility values.

The ligands, *p*-methyl-, *p*-methoxy-, *p*-hydroxy-, *m*-nitro-, and *o*-amino-benzohydroxamic acids, produced the usual violet to violet-black 1:2 compounds. All these compounds dissolve in alcohols, forming red to orange-red solutions. These, however, on evaporation of the alcohol, gave not the esters, but the original oxo-hydroxo-bis-hydroxamato-vanadium (V) complexes.

o-Hydroxybenzohydroxamic acid gave a blue-violet 1:2 complex, soluble in ethanol, producing a brownish purple colour instead of the usual orange-red colour.

Of the different hydroxamic acids, so far studied, only with benzohydroxamic acid, phenylacetylhydroxamic acid, *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, and α -naphthylhydroxamic

*Reactions of the β -naphthylhydroxamic acid will be reported later.

acid, it has been possible to isolate the red-coloured ester compounds. With the other ligands, the reaction with alcohols gave only the red-coloured solution but, not the esters in solid state. The reactions in the case of these latter reagents proceeded, presumably, to the extent of the formation in solution of the alcohol adducts. These alcohol molecules are held to the 'OH' group in $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}'\text{H})_2]$ through hydrogen bonding. A possible explanation of the failure of *p*-methyl-, *p*-methoxy-, and *p*-hydroxy-benzohydroxamic acids, as compared to *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, to give rise to the ester compounds in the solid state, might be offered from an appreciation of the electron-releasing and electron-withdrawing property of the substituents in the benzene nucleus of the hydroxamic acids. The presence of the electron-releasing groups (methoxy, amino, methyl, and hydroxy) in the *ortho* and *para* positions is expected to lower the acid characteristics of the 'OH' group attached to vanadium. This results in lowering of the chances of esterification. On the other hand, the nitro group in the *para* position is known as an electron-withdrawing group. This would make the 'OH' group more acidic, which would facilitate the formation of ester compounds. Though the nitro group in *meta* position is not expected to alter the characteristics of the ligand functional group to any appreciable extent, we have, however, not succeeded in isolating any ester compound. With α -naphthylhydroxamic acid, due to greater electronegative character of naphthalene nucleus, the acidity of the 'OH' group is expected to be increased. This, in turn, would facilitate the formation of esters.

Phenylacethydroxamic acid and ammonium vanadate in aqueous solution at a *pH* 4 (*ca.*) produces the usual violet, sparingly soluble product. This violet product on allowing to stand in the reaction mixture for about 4-5 hrs. turns intense blue. This change in colour is facilitated by presence of a little more acid or when the reaction mixture is kept warm. The two products gave comparable analytical figures: {Found in blue variety: V, 12.90; N, 7.40; C, 51.05; H, 4.39. Found in violet variety: V, 13.30; N, 7.30; C, 50.01; H, 4.54. Calc. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2]$: V, 13.28; N, 7.29; C, 50.00, H, 4.42%}.

The blue variety, like its violet isomer, also reacted with alcohols, forming the usual red-coloured solution from which the esters could be isolated.

p-Nitro-, *p*-methyl-, *p*-methoxy-, and *m*-nitro-benzohydroxamic acids formed stable vanadium (IV) complexes. Of these ligands, the *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid furnished two varieties of vanadium (IV) complex. On mixing hot aqueous solutions of *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid and vanadyl sulphate and on cooling in ice-water, a light violet-coloured precipitate appeared. The filtrate of this preparation, on further warming on a water bath for about half an hour, deposited a crop of green crystals. The analyses of the violet as also of the green product are identical. {Found in violet variety: V, 11.85; N, 13.10; C, 39.76; H, 2.60. Found in green variety: V, 11.77; N, 12.88; C, 38.84; H, 2.70. Calc. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$: V, 11.89; N, 13.05; C, 39.16; H, 2.33%}.

Both the violet and the green products are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.778$ B.M. and 1.737 B.M. respectively), indicating one unpaired electron. The violet isomer on warming with ethanol produces a red-coloured solution. The green variety does so with more difficulty. A qualitative study of the IR spectra of the two varieties shows that the green form has lesser number of bands than the violet form: Since a *trans* form will generally be less rich in bands than the *cis*, the green form may be considered to have a '*trans*' disposition of the functional groups, whereas in the violet complex, they have '*cis*'

arrangement. A similar conclusion was drawn by Faust and Quagliano² from a study of the infrared spectra of *cis*- and *trans*-tetrammine-dinitro-cobalt (III) salt.

Cinnamylhydroxamic acid reacts with aqueous vanadyl sulphate, forming a light rose-coloured product which, however, changes rather readily to the deep ~~violet~~ ^{purple} equivalent complex. Repeated attempts failed to isolate a product of reasonable purity. With the other ligands, the vanadium (IV) complexes were found to be too readily oxidised to the vanadium (V) state.

TABLE III

Magnetic measurements.

Compounds.	$\chi M(\text{corr}) \times 10^6$.	Diamagnetic correction $\times 10^6$.	μ_{eff} (B.M.).	Temp.
1. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ (<i>p</i> -nitro) violet	1285	164	1.778	35°
2. Do green	1226	164	1.737	32°
3. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ (<i>m</i> -nitro)	1066	164	1.614	30°
4. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1085	164	1.629	30°
5. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1092	173	1.630	31°

In order to confirm the results of our studies on the system vanadium (V)-benzohydroxamic acid in dilute solution, we have further extended our investigation to the reactions of vanadate with phenylacethydroxamic acid, *p*-nitro-, *p*-methoxy-, *p*-amino-, and *o*-hydroxy-benzohydroxamic acids as also with quinaldinhydroxamic acid.

All the above hydroxamic acids, excepting the *o*-hydroxybenzohydroxamic acid, produce with traces of ammonium vanadate at a pH 3-5 in 1:1 aqueous ethanol an intense golden yellow to red colour. The absorption maxima in the visible and the extinction coefficients of these coloured products are recorded in Table IV for comparison along with the absorption maxima and extinction coefficients of the solid 1:2 ester compounds and/or the violet-black compounds in ethanol. The spectra of the latter category of complexes reveal variations in the nature as also in the extinction. This therefore indicates that the species involved in dilute solution is different from the ester compounds. It is interesting to note that the ethanol solutions of the violet-black compounds exhibit spectra identical in nature with those of the corresponding esters in ethanol. Job's method of continued variation around pH 3 revealed a metal: ligand ratio of 1:3 for the golden yellow species in dilute solution. Further continued variation between ester compound (*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid and phenylacethydroxamic acid) and the corresponding hydroxamic acid under identical conditions indicated a 1:1 interaction. This further confirms that the coloured species in dilute solution has an empirical metal: ligand ratio of 1:3. As discussed in an earlier communication¹, unambiguous structure is difficult to propose in such cases.

TABLE IV

Complex.	Solvent.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Molar extinction. litre. mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ .
1. [VO(OH) (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .CONHO) ₂] blue	Ethanol	420-430m μ *	1080
2. Do violet	"	420-430*	1110
3. [VO(OC ₂ H ₅) (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .CONHO) ₂]	"	430*	980
4. Vanadium phenylacethydroxamate	1 : 1 Aq. ethanol	440*	3120
5. [VO(OH) (C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH.CONHO) ₂]	Ethanol	450*	2040
6. [VO(OC ₂ H ₅)(C ₁₁ H ₈ NO ₂) ₂]	"	440*	1760
7. [VO(OH) (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂) ₂]	"	430	1312
8. [VO(OH) (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	"	430	1900
9. [VO (OCH ₃) (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	"	430	1800
10. Vanadium <i>p</i> -nitrobenzohydroxamate	1 : 1 Aq. ethanol	430	2560
		400	6000
11. [VO(OH) (<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	Ethanol	450*	2169
12. Vanadium <i>p</i> -methoxybenzo- hydroxamate	1 : 1 Aq. ethanol	460-470*	4312
13. [VO(OH) (<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	Ethanol	430*	1300
14. [VO(OH) (<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	"	470*	1720
		600*	1180
15. [VO(OH) (<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	Pyridine	620*	3560
16. Vanadium salicylhydroxamate	1: 1 Aq. ethanol	470*	4240
17. [VO(OH) (<i>o</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CONHO) ₂]	Ethanol	470*	1900
18. Vanadium anthranilhydroxamate	1 : 1 Aq. ethanol	470*	3400
		430*	3240

*The wave length where a peak [somewhat] was observed. The extinctions of the rest were calculated at the particular wave length mentioned.

o-Hydroxybenzohydroxamic acid alone shows a notable difference. In dilute solution and in presence of a limited amount of reagent, a deep blue solution is obtained at *pH* about 3, whereas in presence of a large excess of the ligand and at the same *pH*, a stable golden yellow product results. Bhaduri and Rây³ utilised the blue-coloured species for colorimetric purpose. They reported that this was a 1:1 species. We have re-investigated this system and have confirmed their findings. No mention, however, was made of the golden yellow species; instead, a violet colour was observed by them in presence of a large excess of the ligand. Since this golden yellow species appeared to be stable only when a large excess of the ligand was present, it was not feasible to establish its identity through continued variation methods. Having recourse to the other similarly coloured products with earlier ligands, it will not, however, be unreasonable to assume that it is a higher complex. Since the blue-coloured species has no parallel in other hydroxamic acids, it may be assumed that in addition to the hydroxamic acid group, the phenolic 'OH' also participates in the colour formation in dilute solution. Further, the blue-coloured species was not retained on either a cation exchanger (Amberlite IR-120) or an anion exchanger (Amberlite IR-400). The possible structures [VO₂R'H]⁻, [VO(OH)₂R'H]⁻, [V(OH)₂R'H]⁺ etc. are therefore ruled out. The complex is probably a neutral species of one of these types: [VO(OH)R'H], [V(OH)₂R'H] etc. (R'H₂=a molecule of salicylhydroxamic acid).

3. *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 97; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 103.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents were prepared by following standard methods.⁴

The reagents, *p*-nitro- and *m*-nitro-benzohydroxamic acids, phenylacetylhydroxamic acid, and salicylhydroxamic acid³, were obtained as the free acid because the potassium salts were comparatively soluble. The anthranil- and quinaldino-hydroxamic acids were prepared by following the method of Dutta⁵. The other reagents were obtained as their potassium salts, following the method of benzohydroxamic acid.

1. *Oxo-hydrozo-bis-phenylacetylhydroxamate-vanadium* (V): (a). *Violet Variety*.—An aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.1 g.), dissolved in 20-25 ml of water, was added to an aqueous solution of phenylacetylhydroxamic acid (0.6-0.7 g. in 100-150 ml water). On adjusting the pH to about 3-4 by addition of dilute H_2SO_4 (4*N*), the wine-red coloured solution deposited a violet, sparingly soluble, crystalline precipitate. The product was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$. $\chi_g = -0.2 \times 10^{-6}$ (32°). {Found: C, 50.01; H, 4.54; N, 7.30; V, 13.30. $[VO(OH)(C_8H_8NO_2)_2]$ requires C, 50.0; H, 4.42; N, 7.29; V, 13.28%}.

(b) *Blue Variety*.—To the initially separated violet compound (as in 1a), a small amount of acid was added and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for about 4 to 5 hrs. The violet precipitate changed completely into an intense blue crystalline substance which was filtered, washed well with hot water, and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$. $\chi_g = -0.21 \times 10^{-6}$ (32°). (Found: C, 51.05; H, 4.39; N, 7.40; V, 12.8%).

2. *Oxo-methoxo-bis-phenylacetylhydroxamate-vanadium* (V).—The violet compound prepared as in (1) was dissolved in 10-15 ml of methanol; the red-coloured solution formed was then refluxed on a water bath for 4 hour and filtered; the filtrate on cooling in ice water deposited beautiful, silky, ruby-red crystals. These were then filtered and dried over $CaCl_2$. $\chi_g = -0.2 \times 10^{-6}$ (32°). {Found: C, 51.04; H, 4.83; N, 7.10; V, 12.60. $[VO(OCH_3)(C_8H_8NO_2)_2]$ requires C, 51.25; H, 4.77; N, 7.03; V, 12.81%}.

3. *Oxo-ethoxo-bis-phenylacetylhydroxamate-vanadium* (V) was prepared as in (2), using ethanol (10 ml) instead of methanol and refluxing for an hour. Hard, shining, ruby-red crystals were obtained from the red solution on cooling in ice water. {Found: V, 12.25; N, 6.84. $[VO(OC_2H_5)(C_8H_8NO_2)_2]$ requires V, 12.38; N, 6.79%}.

4. *Oxo-hydrozo-bis-cinnamylhydroxamate-vanadium* (V) was prepared as in (1a) from sodium cinnamylhydroxamate (0.5g. in 250-350 ml of cold water) and ammonium vanadate (1g.) at pH 4-5. Violet-black crystalline precipitate formed was then digested on a water bath, filtered, washed with hot water, and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$. {Found: V, 12.53; N, 6.88. $[VO(OH)(C_9H_8NO_2)_2]$ requires V, 12.50; N, 6.86%}.

The above violet-black compound dissolved in methanol (25ml) on refluxing on a water bath, forming a deep red solution. The heating was continued for about 6 hrs. and

4. Blatt, *Org. Syn. Coll. Vol. II*, p. 67.

5. Dutta, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 311; 1958, 35, 243; 1959, 36, 399.

filtered; the residue left on evaporation of the alcohol was the same violet-black compound. $\{ \text{Found: V, 12.6; N, 6.90. } [\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 12.50; N, 6.86\%} \}$.

5. *Oxo-hydrozo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)*.— α -Naphthylhydroxamic acid (0.4 g.) in water was dissolved in excess of NaOH solution as the free acid was poorly soluble in water. Aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.1 g.) was then added to the reagent solution and the pH adjusted to 3-4 by adding dilute H_2SO_4 to the cooled solution. A violet crystalline precipitate formed was filtered, washed with a large volume of water, and dried over CaCl_2 . $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.70; N, 6.60. } [\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 11.18; N, 6.14\%} \}$.

6. *Oxo-methoxo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)* was obtained as a red product from the violet compound (prepared as in 5) and methanol (40-50 ml), following the procedure of (2). $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.64; N, 5.67. } [\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 10.85; N, 5.95\%} \}$.

7. *Oxo-ethoxo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)* was prepared as in (6), using EtOH (35-40 ml) in place of MeOH. $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.34; N, 5.70. } [\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 10.53; N, 5.78\%} \}$.

8. *Oxo-propoxo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)* was prepared as in (6), using propanol^l (5-7 ml) in place of methanol. $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.15; N, 5.40. } [\text{VO}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 10.24; N, 5.62\%} \}$.

9. *Oxo-propoxo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)* was obtained as brick-red crystals, following the procedure of (6), using isopropanol (5 ml) instead of methanol. $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.29; N, 5.24. } [\text{VO}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 10.24; N, 5.62\%} \}$.

10. *Oxo-butoxo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V)*.—The brick-red solid was prepared by following the method of (6), using butanol^l (5 ml) instead of methanol. $\{ \text{Found: V, 10.13; N, 5.51. } [\text{VO}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 9.96; N, 5.46\%} \}$.

11. *Amyl Ester of (oxo-hydrozo-bis- α -naphthylhydroxamate-vanadium(V))* was prepared as in (6), using amyl^l alcohol (4-5 ml). $\{ \text{Found: C, 60.45; H, 5.21. } [\text{VO}(\text{OC}_5\text{H}_{11})(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2] \text{ requires C, 61.60; H, 5.13\%} \}$.

12. *Oxo-hydrozo-bis-quinaldinohydroxamate-vanadium(V)*.—Aqueous solutions of ammonium vanadate (0.1 g.) and quinaldinohydroxamic acid hydrochloride (0.6 g. in a large volume of boiling water) were mixed and acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 (4*N*) when a violet-black crystalline precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed well with hot water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . $\{ \text{Found: V, 11.40; N, 12.0. } [\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2] \text{ requires V, 11.13; N, 12.22\%} \}$.

13. *Oxo-hydrozo-bis-p-nitrobenzohydroxamate-vanadium(V)* was obtained as a crystalline violet precipitate from *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (0.5 g.) in warm water (125-150 ml) and aqueous ammonium vanadate (0.1 g.), following the method of (1a). $\{ \text{Found: V, 11.00; N, 12.45. } [\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \text{ requires V, 11.43; N, 12.55\%} \}$.

14. *Oxo-methoxo-bis-p-nitrobenzohydroxamate-vanadium(V)*, the brick-red compound, was prepared from the violet compound as in (13) and methanol (20 ml), following the

method of (3). {Found: V, 10.94; N, 12.17. $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires V, 11.08; N, 12.17%}.

15. *Oxo-ethoxo-bis-p-nitrobenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V) was prepared by following the method of (14), using ethanol (15 ml) in place of methanol and heating for about 3 to 3½ hrs. {Found: V, 10.58; N, 11.60. $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires V, 10.76; N, 11.81%}.

16. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-p-methylbenzohydroxamato vanadium* (V) was prepared, following the method of (1a). {Found: V, 13.10; N, 7.31. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires V, 13.28; N, 7.29%}.

17. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-p-methoxybenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V) was prepared by following the method of (1a), using potassium *p*-methoxybenzohydroxamate instead of phenylacetohydroxamic acid. {Found: V, 11.90; N, 6.50. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires V, 12.26; N, 6.73%}.

18. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-p-hydroxybenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V).—An aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.1g. in 5 ml water) was added to a concentrated aqueous solution of *p*-hydroxybenzohydroxamic acid (0.5 g. in about 20-25ml water). The deep pink solution, first formed, deposited a violet-black crystalline precipitate on acidification with dilute H_2SO_4 (4*N*) to a pH 3-4. It was then filtered, washed well with water, and dried over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 12.84; N, 7.10. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires V, 13.14; N, 7.21%}. The compound dissolves in methanol producing the usual red colouration. This on refluxing for 2 hrs., however, did not yield any red ester compound on cooling; but on evaporation of the alcohol, the original violet-black compound was obtained.

19. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-m-nitrobenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V) was obtained by following the method of (13), using *m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid instead of *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid. {Found: V, 11.10; N, 12.72. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires V, 11.43; N, 12.55%}.

20. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-aminobenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V).—A concentrated aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.1g.) and sodium salt of *o*-aminobenzohydroxamic acid (0.5 g.) were mixed when a violet colour developed. This was then adjusted to pH 5 by dilute acetic acid when the sparingly soluble, dark violet, crystalline precipitate was obtained. It was then filtered, washed well with water, and dried over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 12.95; N, 14.62. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2]$ requires V, 13.21; N, 14.50%}.

21. *Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-hydroxybenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (V) was prepared, following the method of (20), adjusting the pH to about 3-4 by dilute H_2SO_4 (2*N*). The sparingly soluble, blue-violet precipitate was obtained. {Found: V, 12.75; N, 7.12. $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3)_2]$ requires V, 13.14; N, 7.21%}.

22. *Oxo-bis-p-nitrobenzohydroxamato-vanadium* (IV): (a). *Violet Variety*.—An aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.5 g.) was added to a hot solution of *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (0.8g. in 150 ml water) and the solution heated on a boiling water bath for about 5-10 minutes, when the colour of the solution became light violet. This was then cooled in ice water when the crystalline violet-black compound, mixed with some floccs, settled at the bottom. These were then filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 .

The compound is slightly soluble in water. {Found: C, 39.76; H, 2.60; N, 13.10; V, 11.85. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires C, 39.16; H, 2.33; N, 13.05; V, 11.88%}.

(b). *Green Variety*.—The filtrate from the above preparation was then again heated on a boiling water bath for 10 to 15 minutes when the crystalline green product was deposited even while hot. The same green compound was also obtained from VOSO_4 and *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (as in 22a) by heating on a water bath for a longer period (30-45 mins.). {Found: C, 38.84; H, 2.70; N, 12.88; V, 11.77%}.

23. *Oxo-bis-p-methylbenzohydroxamate-vanadium(IV)*.—Potassium *p*-methylbenzohydroxamate (0.45 g.) in water was acidified with dilute acetic acid to a pH 4.5 (ca.). An aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.25 g.) was then added to the above reagent solution when the crystalline dark grey-violet compound deposited was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 13.45; N, 7.80. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_4)_2]$ requires V, 13.89; N, 7.62%}.

24. *Oxo-bis-p-methoxybenzohydroxamate-vanadium(IV)* was prepared by the action of an aqueous solution of VOSO_4 with an aqueous solution of potassium-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamate in the ratio of 1:3. The product was a rose-violet crystalline compound. {Found: V, 12.88; N, 6.98. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3)_2]$ requires V, 12.78; N, 7.01%}. This as well as the compound (23) dissolved in ethanol, yielding initially a red-violet solution which deepened to a deep orange solution with time, indicating oxidation to vanadium (V) state.

25. *Oxo-bis-m-nitrobenzohydroxamate-vanadium(IV)* was prepared by heating a mixture of aqueous solutions of *m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (0.45 g. in 100 ml water) and vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g.) on a water bath for about 10-15 minutes. The crystalline, light rose-red product deposited was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 11.65; N, 12.84. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ requires V, 11.88; N, 13.05%}. This is also soluble in alcohol, producing a pale red-violet colour which ultimately changes to a deep orange-coloured solution.

Absorption Spectra

The absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in ethanol. The spectra of the coloured species involved in colorimetry were recorded in presence of a large excess of the corresponding reagent (vanadium: reagent about 1:150) (Figs. 1-5).

Job's Method of Continued Variation

The experimental procedure, as was given in the earlier paper under vanadium benzohydroxamic acid¹, was followed here for the substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids as well (Figs. 6-10).

In the context of the above results with monohydroxamic acids, it appears that a study of vanadium complexes of dihydroxamic acids may be worthwhile. Besides, the coordination complexes of the closely related substituted hydroxylamines, e.g. $\text{R}_1-\text{N}-\text{OH}$

with vanadium may be a promising field of further studies. Further results in this series and the utility of the substituted hydroxamic acids will be reported in due course.

FIG. 1

- (A) $\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CONHO})_2$ (blue), 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 2 cm.
 (B) $\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CONHO})_2$ (violet), 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 2 cm.
 (C) $\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CONHO})_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 2 cm.
 (D) Vanadium, 0.00025 *M*; phenylacethydroxamic acid, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.00; cell, 0.5 cm.

FIG. 2

- (A) $\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CH}\text{CONHO})_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (B) $\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{CONHO})_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (C) $\text{VO}(\text{OH})[p\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO}]_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (D) Vanadium, 0.00025 *M*; potassium *p*-methoxybenzohydroxamate, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH, 3.00; cell, 0.5 cm.

FIG. 3

- (A) $\text{VO(OH)(C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N.CONHO)}_2$, 0.00025*M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (B) $\text{VO(OH)(o-NH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.CONHO)}_2$, 0.00025*M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (C) Vanadium, 0.00025*M*; sodium anthranilhydroxamate, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.00; cell, 0.5.

FIG. 4

- (A) $\text{VO(OH)(p-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.CONHO)}_2$, 0.00025*M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (B) $\text{VO(OCH}_3\text{)(p-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.CONHO)}_2$, 0.00025*M*; solvent, ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (C) $\text{VO(OH)(m-NO}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.CONHO)}_2$, 0.00025*M*; solvent ethanol; cell, 1 cm.
 (D) Vanadium, 0.00025*M*; *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH, 3.00; cell, 0.5 cm.

FIG. 5

- (A) $\text{VO}(\text{OH}) (\text{o}-\text{OH}. \text{C}_6\text{H}_4. \text{CONHO})_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol.
 (B) Vanadium, 0.00025 *M*; salicylhydroxamic acid, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; *pH*, 3.10.
 (C) Vanadium, 20 ml of 0.001 *M*; salicylhydroxamic acid, 20 ml of 0.001 *M*. Total volume = 60 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; *pH* 3.02.
 (D) Vanadium, 13.3 ml; salicylhydroxamic acid, 26.7 ml.; Other conditions same as in (C).
 (E) Vanadium, 8 ml; salicylhydroxamic acid, 32 ml. Other conditions same as in (C).
 (F) $\text{VO}(\text{OH}) (\text{o}-\text{OH}. \text{C}_6\text{H}_4. \text{CONHO})_2$, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, pyridine.

FIG. 6

- (A) Vanadium, 0.001 *M*; phenylacethydroxamic acid, 0.001 *M*; metal + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; *pH*, 3.02.
 (B) Other conditions, same as in (A).
 (C) Vanadium 0.001 *M*; quinaldinohydroxamic acid, 0.001 *M*; metal + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; *pH*, 3.04.
 (D) Other conditions, same as in (C).

FIG. 9

- (A) Complex $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(p\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO})_2]$, 0.0005M; *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, 0.0005M; complex + reagent = 40ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH, 3.00.
- (B) Conditions same as in (A).
- (C) Complex $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CONHO})_2]$, 0.0007M; phenylacethydroxamic acid, 0.007M; complex + reagent = 30ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH, 3.00.
- (D) Conditions, same as in (C).

FIG. 10

Vanadium, 0.001M; salicyhydroxamic acid, 0.001M; metal + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.02; wave length, 550 m μ .

The reaction of the black oxo-hydroxo-bis-hydroxamato-vanadium (V) complexes with alcohol to produce characteristic red colour may be favourably utilised for detection of alcohols. This as also the rate of formation of the red colour is now under investigation.

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